

The Impact of Learning Motivation and Facilities for the Result of Social Subject in SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

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The problem in this research is the low results of students' social studies learning in the learning process. This research aims to determine the influence of motivation and learning facilities on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. The variables in this research are learning motivation and learning facilities as independent variables and learning outcomes as the dependent variable. This type of research is quantitative research, with the research population being Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year, consisting of 7 classes with a total of 223 students and a research sample of 146 students of Class VIII SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar in total. Simple random sampling. Data collection techniques use instruments: (1) Learning Motivation questionnaire, (2) learning facilities questionnaire, and (3) learning outcomes questionnaire. The results of this study show that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence of parental income on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value is calculated learning motivation, namely showing the tcount value > ttable (3,382 > 1.655) and significant value (0.001 < 0.05), which means that this variable is significant. (2) there is a positive and significant influence of learning facilities on learning outcomes, this result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of the learning facilities shows the t calculated value > ttable (2,240 > 1.655) and significant value (0.027 < 0.05) which means that this variable is significant. (3) parental income and learning facilities jointly influence learning outcomes, these results can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value shows the calculated f value > ftable (5.776 > 3.06) and significant value (0.004 < 0.05). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.075, which means that 7.5% of the variables of parental income and learning facilities have an influence on student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 92.50% is the influence of other variables that are not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

National education is a conscious and planned effort to create learning facilities and learning processes so that students actively develop their potential to have spiritual, religious strength, self-control, habits, intelligence and skills needed for themselves, society, nation and state. The school's effort to produce quality human resources is through education. To achieve maximum learning outcomes there are. According to Mulyasa, in Istirani and Intan Pulungan (2015:62), said that: Learning Motivation is one of the factors that can improve the quality of learning, because students will study seriously if they have high motivation. These include learning motivation factors and learning facilities.

Besides that, a student's good condition in learning will cause the student to be enthusiastic in learning and able to complete his assignments well, in contrast to students who are sick, he has no passion for learning. In the initial stages, it will cause the learning subject to feel a need and want to do something learning activity. This will be seen from students who often come late, do not do their homework (PR), are indifferent when studying, get bored quickly when studying, quickly give up and try to avoid learning activities, so that their own motivation is lacking and can also cause Students are lazy in carrying out the learning process in class.

Learning facilities are the facilities and infrastructure owned by the school that support directly and indirectly the learning process, with the facilities owned by the school it is hoped that it can help students carry out their duties and responsibilities. According to Djamarah (2006:46), learning facilities that support student learning activities will make the teaching and learning process enjoyable and obtain the expected learning outcomes.

Based on initial observations made by researchers at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, there are still inadequate learning facilities. This can be seen from, infocus is still inadequate, only three classes still use infocus, sports facilities are still inadequate, such as sports equipment and sports fields, the social sciences textbooks provided in the library are still inadequate and not comparable. the number of students, and the science laboratory, laboratory equipment and space are still inadequate. This can hinder the use of learning facilities. In general, available and adequate learning facilities will support students' learning activities so that they achieve good learning outcomes.

Learning outcomes are specific questions expressed in behavior and appearance which are realized in written form to describe the expected learning outcomes. Based on the results of initial observations carried out by researchers at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, from a population of 223 class VIII students, researchers obtained student learning outcomes from the Mid-Semester Assessment (PTS) in the Social Sciences subject . seen from the student learning outcomes obtained by class VIII students when taking the social studies subject exam, it is still low or there are still many students who get scores below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM), where the KKM set by the school for the social science subject is 72.

Meanwhile, the social studies teacher hopes that 95% of students will succeed in achieving a score above the KKM in the Mid-Semester Assessment (PTS) exam in the social sciences subject, but in reality, seen from the Mid-Semester Assessment table, many students fail the social studies subject exam, where students who pass In the social studies exam there were only 82 students or 37% and 141 students or 63% did not complete it .

Based on the problems that have been described, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Learning Motivation and Learning

Facilities on Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students in The Subject of Social Sciences at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar."

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Motivation to learn

According to Mulyasa, in Istirani and Intan Pulungan (2015:62), said that: Learning Motivation is one of the factors that can improve the quality of learning, because students will study seriously if they have high motivation. Therefore, to improve the quality of learning, teachers must be able to arouse student motivation so that they can achieve learning goals. So it can be concluded that motivation is an effort that exists within an individual in the form of attitudes, actions and encouragement to act in directing and moving the individual to a behavior so that the desired goal is achieved.

2. Learning Facilities

Learning facilities are learning tools that are used by teachers when teaching and that are used by students to receive the learning material being taught. According to Bafadal in the journal Lela Camellia Cynthia. Et al (2016:9), define, "Learning facilities are all equipment, materials and furniture that are directly used in the learning process at school." From this understanding, it can be stated that learning facilities are all the needs required by students in order to facilitate, expedite and support the implementation of learning activities at school. It can be concluded that facilities are anything that is used directly or indirectly to facilitate and expedite the learning process in order to achieve educational goals. The facilities in question are the learning situations, actions, facilities and infrastructure that students need to study at school or at home.

3. Learning Outcomes

Learning outcomes are specific statements expressed in behavior and appearance which are realized in written form to describe the expected learning outcomes. This behavior can be in the form of concrete, visible facts and hidden facts. According to Novita et al, in the journal I Ga Anggela Heni Krisnayanti and Sandi Wijaya (2022:4), student learning outcomes are an achievement of student success targets that have been set by educators or teachers which can be measured through 3 domains, namely, cognitive, affective, and psychomotor . So it can be concluded that learning outcomes are the extent to which learning material is mastered due to the process of changing students' attitudes and behavior in the various aspects they are engaged in so that there is a clear difference between before the student learns and after learning.

METHODS

Method The research used is a quantitative research approach. This research uses a quantitative approach, which is aimed at explaining the influence of learning motivation and learning facilities on learning outcomes. Quantitative research methods are a process of discovering knowledge using data in the form of numbers as a tool for analyzing information about what you want to know.

Based on the researcher's title " the influence of learning motivation and learning facilities on the learning outcomes of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar" . This research was carried out at SMPN 7 Pematang Siant ar from May to September 2023 . The population in this study were all students in class VIII of

SMPN 7 Pematang Siantar 7 classes totaling 223 students . The sample in this research was 146 students.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Result

Research Instrument Trial Results

Instrument Validity Test

Based on the results of validity calculations using the SPSS version 21 program, it was found that of the 40 statement items from variables X1 and X2, there were 36 valid statement items and 4 invalid items. As a result of the trial, 35 samples obtained valid and reliable statements, with an r-table value of 0.334.

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.334$ while items that have a correlation value $(r) < 0.334$ are invalid items . This can be concluded that for the questions it is known that there are 60 items that have a correlation value $(r) > 0.334$ and as many as 6 questions $(r) < 0.334$, it is known that 40 questions have valid data and 4 are invalid. Therefore, the 4 invalid questions were not used for further research .

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level $(\alpha = 0.05)$ then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the question is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is 0.792 and 0.886, in the r -table it is obtained = 0.334. So $r_{count} > r_{table}$ and if the Cronbach Alpha value (0.792 and 886) is > 0.334 . From the results of calculating the reliability of learning motivation and learning facilities, it can be concluded that the instruments in the questionnaire used are reliable.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Data Normality Test

Table 1. Normality Test Results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residuals
N		146
Normal Parameters, b	Mean	,000000
	Std. Deviation	8,89672009
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,065
	Positive	,065
	Negative	-,049
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,780
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,577

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Based on the calculation results in table 1, the Kolmogorov Smirnov value for all variables is $0.583 > 0.05$, meaning that the existing variables are normally distributed.

Linear Test

To test the linearity of the data, researchers used the SPSS version 21 application. The basis for making decisions is:

- a. If the sig value. deviation from linearity > 0.05 , then there is a linear relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.
- b. If the sig value. deviation from linearity < 0.05 , then there is no linear relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Table 2
X1 and Y Linearity Test Results

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
(Combined)			3315,700	35	94,734	1,147	,291
Learning Outcomes *	Between Groups	Linearity	522,848	1	522,848	6,328	.013
		Deviation from Linearity	2792.852	34	82.143	,994	,489
Learning Motivation	Within Groups		9088.410	110	82,622		
Total			12404.110	145			

Based on the results of the linearity test, it is known that the sig value, *deviation from linearity* is $0.489 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between learning motivation and learning outcomes.

Table 3
2 and Y Linearity Test Results
ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
(Combined)			1533,786	31	49,477	,519	,981
Learning Outcomes *	Between Groups	Linearity	6,039	1	6,039	,063	,802
		Deviation from Linearity	1527,747	30	50,925	,534	,975
Learning Facilities	Within Groups		10870.324	114	95,354		
Total			12404.110	145			

Based on the results of the linearity test, it is known that the sig value, *deviation from linearity* is $0.975 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between learning facilities and learning outcomes.

Simple Linear Regression Test

Table 4 . Simple Linear Regression Test Results Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	61.102	7,206		8,479	,000
Motivation to learn	,420	.124	,391	3,382	,001
Learning Facilities	,348	,156	,258	2,236	,027

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes (Source: data processed from SPSS version 21)

In the table above it is known that the constant value (a) is 61.012, shows that if the learning motivation variable to improve learning outcomes is 0.420 and learning facilities to improve learning outcomes is 0.348, then the variables X1 and So the regression equation can be written:

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 61.012 + 0.348 (X2)$$

This equation can be explained:

Using this equation, you can predict the value of Y based on the given X1 and X2. For example, if X1 is 54 and X2 is 55, then the prediction for Y will be:

$$Y = 61.012 + 0.420 (54) = 83.69$$

This means that when X1 is 54, it can be expected that Y will have a value of approximately 83.69 .

$$Y = 61.012 + 0.348 (55) = 81.15$$

This means that when X2 is 55, it can be expected that Y will have a value of approximately 81.15 .

Multiple linear regression test

Table 5. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	61.102	7,206		8,479	,000
Motivation to learn	,420	.124	,391	3,382	,001
Learning Facilities	,348	,156	,258	2,236	,027

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes (Source: data processed from SPSS version 21)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the constant value (a value) is 61,102 and for the learning motivation value (b1) it is 0.420 and for the learning facility value (b2) it is 0.348 so that the multiple linear regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 61.102 + 0.420X_1 + 0.348X_2 + 7.206$$

1. A constant of 61.102 means that the consistent value of the learning outcome variable is 61.102
2. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.420 and X2 is 0.348. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the influence of variable X1 and variable X2 on Y is positive.

Partial Test (t)

Table 6. t test results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	61.102	7,206		8,479	,000
Motivation to 1 learn	,420	.124	,391	3,382	,001
Learning Facilities	,348	,156	,258	2,236	,027

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes (*Source: data processed from SPSS version 21*)

From the table above it can be seen that the t test results for the Learning Motivation variable (X₁) show a calculated t value of 3.382 and a significance value of 0.001. Thus the calculated t value > t table (3.382 > 1.655) and the sig value (0.001 < 0.05). This means that H1 is accepted, which means it exists The influence of learning motivation on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Meanwhile, the t test results for the Learning Facilities variable (X₂) show a calculated t value of 2.236 and a significance value of 0.027. Thus the calculated t value > t table (2.236 > 1.655) and the sig value (0.027 < 0.05). This means that H2 is accepted, where the learning facilities variable (X2) has an influence on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, F_{count} is compared with F_{table} with the following conditions :

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then H_a is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

Table 7. F Test Results

ANOVA ^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	924.169	2	462,084	5,756	.004 ^b
Residual	11479.941	143	80,279		
Total	12404.110	145			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

b. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Facilities, Learning Motivation

^{calculated} F value is 5.756 and the sig value is 0.004 . Thus the ^{calculated} $F > F_{table}$ (5.756 > 3.06) and the sig value (0.004 < 0.05). This means that H_3 is accepted where together there is an influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Facilities on the Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 8. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary ^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,273 ^a	,075	,062	8,960

a. Predictors: (Constant), Learning Environment, Learning Facilities

b. Dependent Variable: Learning Motivation

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the coefficient of determination in this study is an *R square value* of 0.0 75 . The coefficient value of 0.0 75 is equal to 7 , 5 0 % . This value means that the independent variables Learning Facilities and Learning Environment contribute an influence of only 7.5 % to the Learning Motivation of Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar . Meanwhile 9 2 , 5 0 % is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research.

Discussion

The results of the classical assumption test, the above normality test are the main requirements to be able to proceed to the multiple regression analysis test with the data having a normal distribution and a significance level of > 0.05 . In the variables of learning motivation and facilities for learning outcomes, students have a normal distribution between variables with a significant level of 0.583 > 0.05, and based on Figure 4.1 the normal p-plot curve can be seen that the distribution of data is around

the diagonal line and follows the diagonal direction, then the values are standardized and meet the normality assumption.

Based on the results of the linearity test, it is known that the sig value, *deviation from linearity* is $0.489 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between learning motivation and learning outcomes. and the results of the linearity test show that the sig value, *deviation from linearity* is $0.975 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between learning facilities and learning outcomes. In the simple linear regression test, it is known that the constant value (a) is 61.012, indicating that if the learning motivation variable to improve learning outcomes is 0.420 and learning facilities to improve learning outcomes is 0.348, then the variables X1 and regression can be written:

$$Y = a + bX$$
$$Y = 61.012 + 0.348 (X2)$$

This equation can be explained:

Using this equation, you can predict the value of Y based on the given X1 and X2. For example, if X1 is 54 and X2 is 55, then the prediction for Y will be:

$$Y = 61.012 + 0.420 (54) + 0.348 (55) = 83.69.$$

This means that when X1 is 54, it can be expected that Y will have a value of approximately 83.69 .

$$Y = 61.012 + 0.348 (55) + 0.420 (54) = 81.15$$

This means that when X2 is 55, it can be expected that Y will have a value of around 81.15. Based on the multiple linear regression test, it is known that the constant value (a value) is 61.102, while the value of learning media (b1) is 0.420 and the value of critical thinking skills (2) is 0.348, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e$$
$$Y = 61.102 + 0.420X_1 + 0.348X_2 + 7.206$$

A constant of 61.102 means that the consistent value of the learning achievement variable is 61.102. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.420 and X2 is 0.348. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X1 and Variable X2 on Y is positive. The results of the t test for the Learning Motivation variable (X_1) show a *calculated t value* of 3.382 and a significance value of 0.001. Thus the *calculated t value* $>$ *t table* ($3.382 > 1.655$) and the sig value ($0.001 < 0.05$). This means that H1 is accepted, which means it exists The influence of learning motivation on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. Meanwhile, the t test results for the Learning Facilities variable (X_2) show a *calculated t value* of 2.236 and a significance value of 0.027 . Thus the *calculated t value* $>$ *t table* ($2.236 > 1.655$) and the sig value ($0.027 < 0.05$) . This means that H2 is accepted, where the learning facilities variable (X_2) has an influence on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar.

calculated F value is 5.756 and the sig value is 0.004 . Thus the *calculated F* $>$ *F table* ($5.756 > 3.06$) and the sig value ($0.004 < 0.05$). This means that H3 is accepted where together there is an influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Facilities on the Learning

Outcomes of Class VIII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. The coefficient of determination value shows that the coefficient of determination in this study is an *R square value* of 0.075. The coefficient value of 0.075 is equal to 7.5 % . This value means that the independent variables are learning motivation and facilities b learning contributes an influence of only 7.5 % to the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar . Meanwhile, 92.5 % is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research, such as learning environment variables, learning discipline, interest in learning, parenting patterns, and so on.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results and discussion in chapter IV, the conclusions that can be put forward in this research are as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Motivation on the Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students in Social Sciences subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) on Learning Motivation (X_1) carried out using SPSS version 21, which shows the *calculated t value* $> t_{table}$ ($3.382 > 1.655$) and a significant value ($0.001 < 0.05$).
2. There is a positive and significant influence between learning facilities on the learning outcomes of class VIII students in social studies subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar . This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (t test) on learning facilities (X_2) carried out using SPSS version 21, which shows the *calculated t value* $> t_{table}$ ($2.240 > 1.655$) and significant value ($0.027 < 0.05$).
3. There is a positive and significant influence between Learning Motivation and Learning Facilities on the Learning Results of Class VIII Students in Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of simultaneous calculations (F test) on Learning Motivation (X_1) and Learning Facilities (X_2) was carried out using SPSS version 21, namely, showing the *calculated f value* $> f_{table}$ ($5.776 > 3.06$) and significant value ($0.004 < 0,05$).

FURTHER STUDY

From the results of research conducted by researchers, there are several suggestions that need to be considered for various parties in order to improve further research as well as the benefits of this research, namely:

1. For Researchers
In this research, it is hoped that it can contribute to the development of knowledge about educational management through studying learning motivation and school learning facilities on learning outcomes, and can be used as a reference and consideration for further research.
2. For Schools
It is hoped that the results of this research can make a positive contribution by increasing learning motivation and the availability of complete learning facilities, in order to raise enthusiasm and improve student learning outcomes.

3. For the University

It is hoped that this research can be used to add references as material for further, more in-depth research in the future .

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REFERENCES

- Bafadal. (2004). *School Equipment Management Theory and Applications*. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksra.
- Djamarah. (2006). *Educational Psychology* . Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Gie The Giang. (2002). *Efficient Ways to Study*. Yogyakarta : Gajah Mada University Press.
- Mudjiman , (2007). *Independent Study* . Surakarta: LPP UNS and UNS Press.
- Istirani and Intan Pulungan. (2015). *Encyclopedia of Education*. Medan
- Siregar. E. (2014). *Learning and Learning Theory* . Bogor: PT Rineka Cipta.
- Sutikno, S , M. and F, Canto. (2007). In P, Intan and Israni. *Encyclopedia of Education*
- Sopiantin, Popi. (2010). *Learning Management Based on Student Satisfaction*. Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia.
- Sugiyono. (2014). *Educational Research Methods, Quantitative Qualitative Approach, and R&D* . Bandung: PT Alfabet. (2016). *Quantitative , Qualitative and R&D Research Methods* . Bandung: PT Alfabet. (2019). *Quantitative Research Methods* . Bandung. Alfabeta. (2022). *Quantitative Research Methods*. Yogyakarta: Alfabeta.
- Hidayana, F, Avita. (2021). The Influence of Complete Learning Facilities on Mathematics Learning Outcomes of Class V Mi Nurul Ulum Madiun Students. *Paradigm Journal, Vol, 11. No 1:190*. https://www.staimmgt.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/10.-EFFECTS_OF_COMPLETENESS_OF_LEARNING_FACILITIES.pdf.
- Nurhalizah, Siti. (2020). The Influence of Learning Motivation and Learning Discipline on Student Learning Achievement in the Financial Accounting Subject Class XI Accounting Skills Competency at SMK Negeri 1 Makassar. *Accounting Articles, pages 3 and 4* . <http://eprints.unm.ac.id/18108/1/>.
- Wicaksono, D, and Iswan. (2019). Efforts to Improve Student Learning Outcomes Through the Implementation of the Problem-Based Learning Model in Class IV

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of Muhammadiyah 12 Pamulang Elementary School, Banten. *Journal*, Vol, 3. No.2:115. <https://jurnal.unj.ac.id/index.php/holistika/article/download/5362>

Cynthia Camellia Lela. et al. (2016). The Influence of Learning Facilities and Learning Motivation on Learning Achievement in Economics Subjects of Class XI IIS Students at SMA Negeri 5 Surakarta in the 2015/1016 Academic Year. *Journal*, <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/bise/article/download/17966/14340>